

PRINT MEDIUM COVERAGE OF HEALTH NEWS: AN ANALYSIS OF THE NATIONAL DAILY ‘THE HINDU’ BEFORE AND AFTER COVID- 19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The news media plays a crucial role in reporting and communicating information related to health security emergencies. (Mach, K.J et al., 2021, Pieri, 2019). Amidst the proliferation of health-related disinformation, traditional media coverage, particularly that of newspapers, is increasingly important. (Shahid et al., 2020). According to Martin (2021), there has been a surge in health reporting in print media in the post-pandemic era. There is a noticeable shift in focus towards increased coverage of health and health-related reports in newspapers, which could help advance the UN Sustainable Development Goal of promoting good health and well-being in the post-pandemic era. The present study aims to analyze newspaper reports on health and related issues, and to investigate the patterns of health communication in print media both before and after the pandemic, as we transition towards a state of relative normalcy. The study employs thematic analysis. The researchers gather data from ‘The Hindu’, a widely circulated national daily. In conducting a comparative analysis, they collected data from two periods: July 10th - August 10th, 2019 (prior to the pandemic) and July 10th - August 10th, 2022 (after the peak period of the pandemic, when most restrictions had been lifted and a sense of normalcy had been restored). The collected data was coded and analyzed using coding sheets that included elements such as the page, column, nature, tone, purpose and others. The study believes that media predominantly print media play a positive role in creating awareness and fighting misinformation. The study brings out the effectiveness of print media in achieving the sustainable development goal of health and wellbeing through regular and more focus on the health issues which are more relevant and current.

Keywords – *Print Medium, Health Communication, SDG, The Hindu.*

INTRODUCTION

Measuring sustainable development in a country can be effectively done by assessing the state of health of its population. This is because good health promotes social cohesiveness, lowers healthcare costs, and enhances productivity, all of which contribute to national growth. Additionally, promoting health over generations helps to bridge the gap in achieving development goals. The mass media plays a vital role in promoting accurate health information, as it serves as a powerful tool for disseminating this information to the public. (Kausar, 2016).

Health communication is an effective technique that can promote behavioural and social change, enhance health outcomes, and assist eliminate health inequities. Media may not tell its readers what to think but certainly is successful in telling what to think about (Cohen, 1963). This resonate the fact that we are living in an era of infodemic (WHO, 2020). It is accepted that health communication delivers information related to health to the communities and thereby enhance their knowledge and create awareness (Beato, 2010). Every time there is an emergency concerning the security of health, it is the news media that play a key role (Mach, K.J et al., 2021, Pieri, 2019). Traditional media coverage more specifically that of the newspaper becomes important amidst the growing disinformation (Shahid et al., 2020) on health and related topics. The post-pandemic has seen a surge in health reporting in print media (Martin 2021). The news media offers a window

into public-interest issues because it is at the intersection of public and policy agendas. As a result, it may be an effective instrument for promoting the health of citizens which are receptive to their demands (Akintola et,al, 2015)

There seems to be a shift of focus where the number of stories covering health and health-related reports in the newspaper has increased thereby putting a thrust on realizing the UN SDG of good health and well-being post-pandemic. India is the second most impacted country in the world after the United States but with far fewer recorded deaths (UNESCO, UNICEF, India Case Study, 2021). Despite the growing dominance of digital media, print media still plays a critical role in disseminating information, particularly regarding health-related news and updates. Individuals seeking information on diseases, prevention, diagnosis, treatment, nutrition, medications, and other factors related to health often rely on print media. Amid the COVID-19 crisis, newspapers played a crucial role in providing extensive news coverage, which helped policymakers address gaps in the system and equip citizens with timely and accurate information. A notable example is the Rajasthan Patrika, one of the leading newspapers in Rajasthan, which published three special daily pages dedicated to COVID-19, named Corona 360, Jeet Jayenge Hum (We Shall Win), and Corona Karmaveer (Hero). These pages served as a valuable resource for the public during this difficult time (Pandey & Kumar, 2020).

As the world moves towards post-pandemic normalcy, it is important to analyse the role of print media in health news coverage before and after the pandemic. News coverage on health is of significance as it has the potential to shape the impression of citizens and policy makers (Byrant & Thompson, 2002). India's adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) places a high priority on health news coverage to achieve the goal of "healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages" (WHO, 2017). SDG 3 envisions universal health coverage and access to quality healthcare, which can be achieved through credible information dissemination by print media. Therefore, print media will play a pivotal role in achieving this goal.

India has a rich tradition of newspapers that has persisted through the post-independence, post-liberalization, and globalization eras. Print media in India are highly regarded for their objective and factual reporting (Saxena, 2021). In the past, newspapers have played a crucial role in spreading awareness about health issues such as the Polio Eradication Mission, AIDS awareness, and the H1N1 flu. They have provided the public with accurate and credible information on these diseases and kept them informed (Pandey & Kumar, 2020). This study aims to analyze the print media coverage of health-related news and articles before and after the pandemic, contributing to a better understanding of this crucial topic.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Print Media for long have played an important role in disseminating health news and creating awareness (Pandey & Kumar, 2021, Saxena, 2021). With Covid-19 the health system across the world was disrupted (India Case Study, Situation Analysis on the Effects of and Responses to COVID-19 on the Education Sector in Asia, 2021, The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2021). This disruption was not just restricted to health sector alone but concerns each and every aspects. Media is no different to this. There are research studies that analyze the health news coverage among the print media (Gupta et,al, 2021 & Saxena, 2021). Studies also look into the media coverage of health news related to covid-19 and the influence of the same is also analyzed (Akintola, Lavis & Hoskins, 2015, Rawat et al, 2021, Manjunatha, S. N. et,al,2019, Tejedor et. al,2020, Pravin et. Al, 2020). On one hand there are studies that bring out the impact of print medium in tackling the covid-19 and on the other there are studies that bring out the impact of covid-19 on print medium and rising infodemic menace with growth of digital networks (Moorhead et, al, 2013, Mheidly & Fares, 2020, Saxena, 2021, Pandya & Lodha, 2021). Studies also reflect the quality of health news that are covered in print media (Oxman et,al, 2022).

RESEARCH GAP

There are studies that look into the health news coverage among print media before covid-19 pandemic and there are studies that analyze the role of media during the pandemic and more specifically impact of print media in spreading awareness of covid-19 only. There are hardly any studies that bring out a comparative analysis of news coverage on health before and in on-going pandemic situation. The present study aims to examine whether there is any change in the outlook of print medium in covering health related issues post covid-19.

MATERIALS & METHOD

Objective: The objective of this study is to analyze newspaper reports on health and related issues, and investigate the extent of health communication coverage in print media before and after the pandemic of covid-19, as we move towards to normalcy.

The study employs content analysis. The researchers used the qualitative method in collecting the data from the Newspaper “The Hindu”, a widely circulated national daily. A comparison of the newspaper coverage of health news pre and post pandemic of the same newspaper is considered for this present comparative analysis. The said data is collected from July 10th - August 10th, 2019, before the onset of the pandemic and July 10th - August 10th, 2022, post the peak period of the pandemic as all restrictions were relaxed and normalcy is restored.

The researchers used a coded template consisting of eight main parameters with sub-categories framed in an inductive manner. The study is descriptive in nature. The thus collected data is coded and analyzed. The coding sheet contains various elements including the page, column, nature, tone, purpose, gender aspect, and others.

The elements/parameters of the study are mentioned below with each parameter having further sub-parameters further add depth to the study.

Total Number of News in newspaper/day
Number of news related to issues on health/day
Age
Gender
Purpose of the said news/article
Tone
Reporting Style based on WHO Strategic Communications Framework for Effective Communications (World Health Organization, 2017)

RESULTS

According to Gupta et al. (2021), the media should ensure that the coverage of health-related news is relevant, timely, and actionable to encourage individuals to respond appropriately. Despite this, the total number of stories related to health still receives relatively less coverage compared to other topics. However, when compared to the amount of space allocated for health communication in 2019, there has been a considerable increase in the news space dedicated to health communication. This suggests that the media is placing more emphasis on spreading awareness about health-related issues, which is a positive development. By providing individuals with more relevant and actionable information, the media can encourage better health-related decision-making and ultimately contribute to the achievement of universal health coverage, a key goal of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Graph 1: Health News Vs Total News

Graph 2: Tone used in Health Communication

Despite an increase in news stories related to health, the overall tone of such stories is predominantly negative. However, there has been a notable rise in news stories with a positive or neutral tone. During a pandemic, effective communication is crucial and requires a call to action, which may explain the more negative tone of some stories. To ensure effective communication during a pandemic, it is essential to communicate openly and transparently with all parties involved. The primary objective of this approach is to eliminate any disparities between the information generated and the information received, thereby ensuring that accurate and relevant information is disseminated (de Las Heras-Pedrosa et al., 2022).

Graph 3: Sub-Tone used in the articles

The analysis reveals that articles published on health tended to adopt a more matter-of-fact tone, often accompanied by a serious nature. However, there has been an increase in the use of an irreverent tone in such articles. This shift in tone may reflect changing attitudes towards health-related topics or a desire to engage readers in a more carefree manner. Nonetheless, it is essential to maintain the accuracy and reliability of the information presented in these articles, regardless of their tone or nature (Gupta et al., 2021).

Graph 4: Purpose of the Health Report

The analysis revealed that the delivery of information has become more important in the print media coverage of health news in 2022 compared to 2019. However, there has been no significant increase in the space devoted to education and awareness purposes, and no health communication was found to be categorized as entertainment or infotainment. Instead, there has been a rise in the publication of news stories that provide timely and relevant information, such as “Concern shifts from COVID to seasonal diseases in Telangana” and “Monkeypox: Vigil in areas in Mysuru and Chamarajanagar district, which border Kerala”. These stories align with the WHO’s framework for effective communication on health-related issues

(WHO, 2017). The increase in the sub-tone of the news stories in 2022 to more serious in nature as compared to those published in 2019 also could be because of growing awareness and increase in interest and accessibility to health care.

There seem to be no change in the age group covered and gender covered pre and post pandemic, the thrust of health communication has been general. Where information on mitigation of disease for all age group and gender seems to be same. 2022 see a slight increase in the stories/articles covering paediatric age as opposed to that on 2019 where all category was followed by youngsters which is now replace with paediatric in 2022.

Graph 5: Age Covered

Graph 6: Gender Covered

The study also examined the gender aspect of health news coverage in both 2019 and 2022. It was found that health news was not specifically aimed at any particular gender and was intended for all. However, there were no health-related articles found in the male and non-binary sections. Interestingly, the coverage of health news related to women was higher in 2019 than in 2022. It is possible that the focus on the pandemic, which affected everyone, led to a decrease in the coverage of health news related to a specific gender. The pandemic highlighted the vulnerability of all genders, and this could be a reason for the lack of stories related to a particular gender.

Graph 7: Style of Reporting

The analysis reveals a significant shift in the reporting style of news stories towards a more timely and relevant approach, in line with the updated WHO effective communication framework. There has been a noticeable increase in news stories that fall under the actionable parameter, indicating a growing focus on prevention and safety measures. The outbreak of Covid-19 has contributed to this shift in outlook, with greater emphasis placed on taking action to prevent the spread of disease and protect public health. Overall, these findings suggest a positive trend towards more responsible and effective health communication in print media.

CONCLUSION

The role of print media in disseminating news and creating awareness is crucial, especially when it comes to health-related issues. With this study, the researchers aimed to analyze whether the COVID-19 pandemic had any significant impact on the coverage of health-related news stories in print media. The study analyzed various parameters, including the number of news stories related to health, age, gender, tone, sub-tone, reporting style, and purpose of the article, based on the WHO Strategic Communications Framework for Effective Communications.

The study findings show that there has been a remarkable increase in the number of news stories and reports related to the health sector in print media since the pandemic. However, it was also observed that the tone of the news stories has become more negative in nature. The purpose of most stories or reports is to provide timely information with a serious tone. The study also found that gender and age are not much focused on in the news coverage, as most news stories are aimed at the general public.

One interesting insight from the study is that there has been an increase in the number of reports that are actionable in style of reporting. With the pandemic, there has been more emphasis on safety precautions, and this has led to an increase in stories that focus on actionable steps to prevent the spread of the disease. The study concludes that print media plays a prominent role in promoting public health and shaping health policies. It is vital for media outlets to ensure that the coverage of health-related news stories is relevant, timely, and actionable, to encourage individuals to respond appropriately. Overall, this study highlights the importance of print media in disseminating health-related information to the public, especially during a crisis like a pandemic.

REFERENCES

1. Akintola, O., Lavis, J. N., & Hoskins, R. (2015). Print media coverage of primary healthcare and related research evidence in South Africa. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 13(1), 68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-015-0051-6>

2. Anwar, A., Malik, M., Raees, V., & Anwar, A. (2020). Role of Mass Media and Public Health Communications in the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Cureus*, 12(9), e10453. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.10453>
3. Bryant, J., & Thompson, S. (2002). *Fundamentals of media effects* (1st ed.). McGraw-Hill.
4. Cohen, B. (1963). *The press and foreign policy*. Princeton University Press.
5. de Las Heras-Pedrosa, C., Jambrino-Maldonado, C., Rando-Cueto, D., & Iglesias-Sánchez, P. P. (2022). COVID-19 Study on Scientific Articles in Health Communication: A Science Mapping Analysis in Web of Science. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1705. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031705>
6. Gupta, M., Keshri, V. R., Konwar, P., Cox, K. L., & Jagnoor, J. (2022). Media coverage of COVID-19 health information in India: A content analysis. *Health Promotion International*, 37(2), daab116. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/daab116>
7. Liu, Q., Zheng, Z., Zheng, J., Chen, Q., Liu, G., Chen, S., Chu, B., Zhu, H., Akinwunmi, B., Huang, J., Zhang, C. J. P., & Ming, W. (2020). Health Communication Through News Media During the Early Stage of the COVID-19 Outbreak in China: Digital Topic Modeling Approach. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(4), e19118. <https://doi.org/10.2196/19118>
8. Mach, K. J., Salas Reyes, R., Pentz, B., Cohn, A. S., Kretzmann, M. B., & Whittington, D. (2021). News media coverage of COVID-19 public health and policy information. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 8(1), 220. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00900-z>
9. Mheidly, N., & Fares, J. (2020). Leveraging media and health communication strategies to overcome the COVID-19 infodemic. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 41(4), 410-420. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-020-00247-w>
10. Moorhead, S. A., Hazlett, D. E., Harrison, L., Carroll, J. K., Irwin, A., & Hoving, C. (2013). A new dimension of health care: systematic review of the uses, benefits, and limitations of social media for health communication. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 15(4), e85. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.1933>
11. Oxman, M., Larun, L., Pérez Gaxiola, G., Alsaïd, D., Qasim, A., Rose, C. J., Bischoff, K., & Oxman, A. D. (2021). Quality of information in news media reports about the effects of health interventions: Systematic review and meta-analyses. *F1000Research*, 10, 433. <https://doi.org/https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal3>
12. <https://sdgs.un.org/publications/sdg-good-practices-2020>
13. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/world-news/social-media-manipulation-a-growing-threat-to-democracies-oxford-study-101610546303113.html>
14. <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/when-a-pandemic-meets-the-era-of-infodemic-67756/>